

adjusted to expose 60-d-old seedlings to 12-14°C air temperature for about 30 d. They were scored for leaf discoloration using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. The F₂ segregation had

165 tolerant (score 3) plants, 380 moderately tolerant (score 5), and 185 susceptible (score 7-9) plants, a perfect 1:2:1 with a nonsignificant χ^2 , that indicated a monogenic inheritance for

leaf discoloration with incomplete dominance for green leaf color. The study is preliminary and no confirmation of the genetic ratio was done with F₃ progenies of backcross generations. □

Cold-tolerant rice variety MDU2

C. Soundrapandian, V. D. Guruswamy Raja, M. Kadambavanasundaram, and P. Rangasamy, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India

Cold damage is a serious constraint to rice yields in the high-altitude zone of Tamil Nadu, where in winter, minimum temperature is 14.5 to 16.0°C. MDU2, a promising cold-tolerant rice variety, was approved by the Tamil Nadu State Varietal Release Committee in Jan 1984 for cultivation in the Cumbum Valley of Madurai district. MDU2 is a hybrid cross of C0-25 and IR8.

In station trials, MDU2 yielded 28%

Average yield^a of MDU2, Madurai, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)		
	Research station trial (1)	Multilocation trials (23) ^b	Rice Coordinated Yield trials (8)
MDU2	3.7	6.1	4.4
IR20	2.9	5.5	3.7
Increase over IR20 (%)	28	11	19

^a Numbers in parentheses indicate sites from which yields were averaged. ^b Trials were conducted at the hot spot area.

more than IR20, and in 23 yield evaluation trials on farmer fields it yielded 11% more. In the rice coordinated yield trials, MDU2 yielded an average 19% more than IR20 (see table).

Spikelet sterility was 23% for MDU2 versus 45% for IR20. MDU2 is a medium-duration (130-135 d), semidwarf variety

with medium tillering ability and good panicle exertion. Grains are medium slender with white kernels, and grain type is acceptable to local consumers. It has some tolerance for leaf blight, gall midge, leafroller, and stem borer, and is recommended for cultivation in the second crop season (Oct-Feb) in the Cumbum Valley. □

Pest management and control DISEASES

Relative amount of rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) in an infected plant

A. Parejarearn, research scholar, IRRI; D. B. Lapis, formerly senior research fellow, IRRI, now associate professor, University of the Philippines at Los Baños College of Agriculture; and H. Hibino, plant pathologist, IRRI

Scoring of rice varieties resistance to RSV has been based on percentage of infected seedlings. Using this method, it is

Reaction of extracts of Mawee and TNI infected with RSV at 30 d after inoculation. IRRI, 1984.

Relative amounts of RSV in infected rice plants on different days after inoculation, IRRI.

Variety	Reaction to RSV ^a	Absorbance at 405 nm of extracts in ELISA		
		30 DAI ^b	45 DAI ^b	60 DAI ^c
Ptb 21	I	0.38 bc	0.48	0.25 ns
Murungakayan	R	0.28 c	0.64	0.32
Mawee	R	0.88 a	1.08	0.75
Balaratawee	R	0.83 a	0.93	0.56
Hathili	R	0.80 a	1.43	0.40
IR22	I	0.84 a	0.91	0.69
IR50	R	0.70 ab	0.87	0.21
TN1	S	0.78 ab	0.91	0.55
Average		0.69	0.90	0.47

^a Results of mass screening were based on 0-30% infection = R, 31-60% infection = I, 61-100% infection = S. DAI= days after inoculation. In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different. ns: not significant. ^b Average A₄₀₅ of extracts at 1:200 dilution. ^c Average A₄₀₅ of extracts at 1:160 dilution.

not clear whether the resistant varieties are resistant to RSV infection or to virus multiplication. Therefore, we determined the resistance of eight selected varieties and the relative amount of the virus in each variety by mass screening and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Seven-d-old seedlings in test tubes were inoculated at five brown plant-

hoppers/seedling and then grown in the greenhouse. One month later, three infected seedlings were selected from each variety and transplanted singly in clay pots. At 30, 45, and 60 d after inoculation, extracts of the whole plant, except the root, were tested by ELISA. γ -globulin was coated with 2.5 μ g/ml and γ -globulin/alkaline phosphate conjugate was diluted 300 times. The relative

amount of virus antigen in the extracts was determined by their absorbance at 405 nm after 30-min incubation with the substrate.

Absorbance decreased as extracts were diluted and RSV was detected in the extracts up to 1/400-1-3200 dilution (by weight) (see figure). The relative amount of RSV was shown as absorbance of ex-

tracts at 1/200 dilution for the test at 30 and 45 d after inoculation and at 1/160 dilution at 60 d.

The relative amount of RSV in individual plants varied among test varieties. Statistically significant differences in the amount of RSV was shown at 30 d after inoculation, but not at 45 and 60 d. Regardless of the test variety, the amount

of RSV was highest at 45 d and declined by 60 d. The relative amount of RSV was less in Ptb 21 and Murungakayan than in the other varieties. There was no significant difference in RSV amount between resistant and susceptible varieties. The results indicate that the resistant varieties tested were resistant to RSV infection but not to virus multiplication. □

Rice grassy stunt (GSV) at high altitudes

V. Mariappan and T. B. Ranganathan, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

The occurrence of GSV and its transmission by the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* were reported in India in 1969. About 100 ha of rice in Tamil Nadu were infected with GSV in 1972, and about 15,000 ha were infested by the virus and its vector in the adjoining state of Kerala in 1973-74.

Since then, the disease has not been observed, despite the presence of large BPH populations. Recently, rice with symptoms similar to those of GSV was found in the Dugalur Valley of the Nilgiris Mountains of Tamil Nadu, where rice is grown on about 3,500 ha. The valley is isolated, and surrounded by 2,000-m-high, densely forested hills. BPH are present in the valley.

Disease symptoms were severe stunting and profuse tillering with narrow erect

leaves, but the plants were green because of high soil N in the valley. Infection was less than 3% in Jagannath, IR20, and local varieties on the horticultural farm in Devala.

Transmission tests using BPH nymphs were conducted. Nymphs lived for 10 d on the source plant, then were transferred to 10-d-old TN1 plants for 5-d inoculation access feeding. One month later, inoculated TN1 plants developed GSV symptoms. □

Pest management and control INSECTS

Brown planthopper (BPH) resistance to a synthetic pyrethroid

Chih-Ning Sun, and Shu-Mei Dai, Entomology Department, National Chung-Hsing University, Taichung, Taiwan 400, China

As a follow-up of the 1979-80 survey that indicated BPH was resistant to permethrin yet susceptible to fenvalerate, in 1982 we monitored BPH susceptibility to four major synthetic pyrethroids and DDT.

Up to 1,000-fold resistance to permethrin was found while resistance levels to 3 other synthetic pyrethroids were much lower, ranging from 10- to 50-fold (see table). All BPH tested were suscepti-

Susceptibility of a susceptible (S) and 6 field strains of BPH to 4 synthetic pyrethroids and DDT in Taiwan, China.^a

Strain	Permethrin		Cypermethrin		Deltamethrin		Fenvalerate		DDT	
	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	RR	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	RR	LC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	RR	LC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	RR	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	RR
Pingtung	2.53	843	9.17	26	14.6	15	5.32	16	—	—
Meinung	2.38	793	5.53	15	39.2	41	13.22	40	0.121	3.7
Hsinshih	3.27	1090	7.53	21	6.7	7	16.67	51	0.114	3.5
Chiayi	2.15	717	4.00	11	9.1	10	4.70	14	0.112	3.4
Taichung	0.22	73	0.48	1	2.0	2	2.30	7	0.062	1.9
Hsinchu	2.64	880	5.29	15	14.3	15	4.80	15	0.128	3.9
S	0.003	—	0.36	—	0.95	—	0.33	—	0.022	—

^a Resistance ratio (RR) = LC₅₀ of field strain divided by LC₅₀ of S strain.

ble to DDT, giving circumstantial evidence that in Taiwan BPH resistance to permethrin is not related to DDT resistance, as it is in insects such as the

housefly, mosquito, and diamondback moth. A metabolic mechanism probably has caused the high BPH resistance to permethrin. □

Changing insect pest status in the Imphal Valley

R. N. Barwal, Indian Council for Agricultural Research (ICAR) Complex for NEH Region, Manipur Centre, Imphal 795001, India

Expanding irrigation facilities in the Imphal Valley allow the growing of two rice crops instead of one. But as cropping

intensity increased, so have populations of common insect pests and sporadic outbreaks of unusual pests.

In 1979, a dry year, stem borers were major pests (see table), with 9.5% dead-hearts at tillering and 16.7% at post-flowering. As rice hectareage increased, populations of other insects such as gall midge, leafroller, leafhoppers, caseworm, grasshoppers, rice bugs, and greenhorned

caterpillar increased, and pest problems developed earlier in the season.

Caseworm became a serious problem when main crop transplanting was delayed to mid-Aug, and gall midge became a problem after the last week of Jul. Leafroller and greenhorned caterpillar disappeared late in the main season, and leafhoppers, grasshoppers, and rice bugs continued through harvest. Thrips